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IMPLICATION OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTS COMMITTEE (PAC) ON PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE ENTITIES IN RWANDA

Case study of Nyamasheke district

Period: 2015-2018

Undergraduate thesis presented in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of Bachelor degree with honor in Economics and Management

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Kibogora , August, 2019

DECLARATION

Declaration by the Candidate

I **NDAYISENGA Innocent** hereby declare that this is my own original work and not a duplication of any similar academic work. It has therefore not been previously or concurrently submitted for any other degree, diploma or other qualification to Kibogora Polytechnic or any other institution. All materials cited in this paper which are not my own have been duly acknowledged.

Signed.....

Date.....

Declaration by the Supervisor

I declare that this work has been submitted for examination with my approval as KP Supervisor

SUPERVISOR'S NAME: Dr. MBONIGABA Celestin, PhD

Signed.....

Date.....

ABSTRACT

The study entitled implication of PAC on performance of local administrative entities was about assessing the contribution of PAC in raising the standards of local entities in terms of performance. This study considered the following objectives; to assess the recommendations raised by PAC based OAG observations in study area, to monitor and evaluate the progressive implementation of PAC and OAG recommendations in study area, to weigh the indicators of performance in study area, to find out the correlation between the performance of local administrative entities and recommendations raised by PAC based OAG in study area.

The researcher used qualitative and quantitative approaches as the study was descriptive. The considered total population were 23 in period of 2015-2018 the universal population was taken as sample size and the data collection instrument which been used were questionnaires where the data were analyzed using SPSS software.

Referring to objective one it is obvious that; in table 6 the researcher sought to know the recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented; in fact it was revealed that PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement. The second objective revealed that 7the time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed; actually it was revealed that regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement. The third objective revealed that table 8 the indicators of performance among local administrative entities due to implementation of recommendation raised by PAC; actually it was revealed that the district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents pointed out that Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations.

By conclusion, it is clear from study area that PAC contribute in performance of local administrative entities found in study area However, they are still facing some challenges in the integration of PAC recommendation in performance of their daily operations and once they are mitigated with proposed strategies the performance will be effectively increased.

DEDICATION

I dedicate this work:

To Almighty God,

To my family,

To my friends, and

Colleagues

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work is a result of collective efforts that worked on it in one way or another. For that reason, my thanks are addressed to the following:

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Be blessed all

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AG	: Auditor General
ANOVA	: Analysis of Variance
APACs	: Association of Public Accounts Committees
ARICs	: Audit Report Implementation Committees
CVI	: content validity Index
EDPRS	: Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy
K.P	: Kibogora Polytechnic
MINECOFIN	: Ministry of Economics and Finance
NAO	: National audit office
NBAs	: Non Budget Agencies
OAG	: Office of Auditor General
PAC	: Public Account Committee
PFM	: Public Financial Management
RRA	: Rwanda Revenue Authority
SAI	: Supreme Audit Institution
SLA	: State Legislative Assembly
SPSS	: Statistical Package for Social Sciences
VFM	: Value For Money

CHAPTER ONE: GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0. INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the background of the study, problem statement, objectives of the study, research questions, significance of the study, limitations of the study and scope of the study.

1.1. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The Committee of Public Accounts, more fashionably called the Public Accounts Committee, was established in 1861 as a "circle of control" during William Gladstone's period as Chancellor of the Exchequer. The PAC operates as a key part of Parliament's control over public spending that combines political oversight with technical expertise. The Committee of Public Accounts (PAC) was first established on 8th April 1861 in England. It owes its origins to the earlier appointment of the Commissioners of Public Account in 1780. The appointment of Commissioners regularized past practice as Parliament was concerned that there should be adequate accounts to show how grants and monies had been paid. The nature of this *ex post* form of control was the main way of bringing transparency to financial processes that were largely a matter of internal control (J. Wehner, 2004).

Globally, over the years, the Association of Public Accounts Committees (APACs) has played a vital role in capacitating PACs Members and support staff so that they could effectively and efficiently perform their oversight and accountability functions (APAC, 2008). The association distinguishes itself as an association concerned with public finance management, empowerment and promotion of sound, accountable and transparent governance in collaboration with oversight committees and other relevant bodies (APAC Annual Report, 2008/09). The association annually organizes a conference in order to provide delegates with an opportunity to interact, network, share best practices and experiences with regard to oversight and accountability matters.

McGee (2002) sought to identify possible courses of action to improve outcomes through more effective use of PACs. Three main priorities were identified:

- **Capacity building** – the need to improve the ability of Parliaments and their PACs to carry out their functions by being provided with adequate resources, training and access to relevant expertise
- **Independence** – that they be free from political or legal constraints that could inhibit them from carrying out their duties diligently

- *Information exchange* – that PACs have the means to exchange information and ideas so as to keep them up-to-date with important developments, changing standards and best practices as they emerge.

Likewise in Africa, the situation is gradually changing for the better. This is primarily due to the requisite skills and knowledge acquired by Members of the PACs when performing oversight responsibilities over the Executives. For instance, in the 2009/10 financial year, the Auditor General Limpopo reported that 67%, 25% and 8% of the Limpopo Provincial Departments in South Africa audited received unqualified, qualified and disclaimer of opinions respectively (Auditor-General of South Africa, 2009/10).

By the way, to ensure performance of local administrative entities performance, PACs recommendations should be implemented and the follow up must be done. For example, the Kenya National Assembly has established a Committee on Implementation. Its mandate includes scrutiny of resolutions of the House including adopted committee reports, petitions and the undertakings given by the government on the floor of the House. The committee examines whether or not such decisions and undertakings have been implemented, the extent to which they have been implemented, and whether such implementation has taken place within the minimum time necessary. The committee also looks into whether or not legislation passed by the House has been operationalized the extent to which such operationalization has taken place and within the minimum time necessary (Auditor general of Kenya, 2010/2011).

Normally, this study was designed to assess deeply the implication of Public accounts Committee on performance of local government entities.

1.2.STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Though PAC establish and implement recommendation to ensure effective performance of local government entities, yet some local entities were found to not perform due to either ineffective execution of recommendation provided with PAC or insufficient follow up of execution of recommendations.

In deputy general auditor opinion, the financial statements give a true and fair view of the state of the financial affairs of **Nyamasheke District**. Further, he accept responsibility for the maintenance of accounting records that may be relied upon in the preparation of financial statements, ensuring adequate systems of internal financial control and safeguarding the assets of the budget agency.

This research was of great importance after finding that some recommendations provided by PAC are not reconsidered by some entities in Nyamasheke district; for instance in 2015; the audit done by PAC in Nyamasheke district reported that according to Article 69 of the Organic Law No. 37/2013 of 12 September 2013 on State Finances and Property, each Chief Budget Manager and Directors of other public bodies are responsible for ensuring implementation of the instructions of the Auditor General of State Finances aimed at improving the effective management of the finances of their entities; actually regarding financial statement, it was revealed that there was a transfers totaling **Frw 2,025,748,886** that were made to Non Budget Agencies (NBAs) during the year were reported as expenditure in financial statements of the District, and yet reports from the Non Budget Agencies show that these Non-Budget Agencies still had unutilized bank balances as at 30 June 2015. For example, the bank statements and financial reports show that sectors had bank balances amounting to **Frw 138,450,674** on Sectors respective bank accounts as at 30 June 2015. Therefore, the reported expenditure is overstated. In this context taking into account the provision of recommendation of PAC, an assessment of the status on the implementation of previous audit recommendations still reveals that most of previous recommendations were not implemented. Only 59% were fully implemented and the remaining 41% are yet to be implemented (Nyamasheke district Audit report, 2015).

In 2016, the report showed that, an assessment of the status on the implementation of previous audit recommendations still reveals that most of previous recommendations were not implemented. 21% of the recommendations were fully implemented, 18% were partially implemented and the remaining 61% are yet to be implemented (Nyamasheke district audit report, 2016).In 2017; regarding auditing opinion, it was shown that according to the financial year (2016/2017) end closing procedures issued by MINECOFIN on 19 June 2017, any outstanding balances of revenue collections not transferred to the district by RRA as at 30 June 2017 should be accounted for by debiting “RRA receivable account” and crediting “transfers from RRA.” Contrary to these guidelines, It was noted that revenue amounting to **Frw 26,945,622** which had

been collected by RRA but not yet transferred to the District was only disclosed and not recorded as a receivable from RRA; following other kind of audit done in this period and following the Article 69 of the Organic Law No. 37/2013 of 12 September 2013 on State Finances and Property, each Chief Budget Manager and Directors of other public bodies are responsible for ensuring implementation of the instructions of the Auditor General of State Finances aimed at improving the effective management of the finances of their entities. It was identified that an assessment of the status on the implementation of previous audit recommendations still reveals that most of previous recommendations were not implemented. 38% of the recommendations were fully implemented, 24% were partially implemented and the remaining 38% are not yet implemented (Nyamasheke district Audit report, 2017).

Regarding deputy general auditor opinion, the matters including; proper books of account have not been maintained and the financial statements do not give a true and fair view of the financial position of Nyamasheke District as at 30 June 2016, and of its financial performance and its cash flows for the year then ended in accordance with the guidelines provided by Ministerial Order N°001/16/10/TC of 26/01/2016 relating to financial regulations and Organic Law N° 12/2013/OL of 12/09/2013 on State Finances and Property (deputy auditor general, 2017).

Thus, this study investigated the role of PAC in facilitating local administrative committee to perform effectively by giving recommendations and evaluate related issues met in their correlation.

1.3.OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.3.1. General objective

The main purpose of this research is to« assess the role of PAC on performance of local administrative entities in Nyamasheke district. »

1.3.2. Specific objectives

This research followed the indicated objectives:

1. To assess the recommendations raised by PAC based OAG observations in Nyamasheke district.
2. To monitor and evaluate the progressive implementation of PAC and OAG recommendations in Nyamasheke district.
3. To weigh the indicators of performance at Nyamasheke District
4. To find out the correlation between the performance of Nyamasheke District and recommendations raised by PAC based OAG in Nyamasheke district.

1.4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are recommendations raised by PAC based OAG observations in Nyamasheke district?
2. How and at which extent implementation of PAC and OAG recommendations are done in Nyamasheke district?
3. What are indicators of performance at Nyamasheke District?
4. Is there any correlation between the performance of Nyamasheke District and recommendations raised by PAC based OAG in Nyamasheke district?

1.5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The present research is of great importance to diverse careers; in fact, to the researcher, Rwandan government sector (for local administrative entities), Rwandan education sector and to K.P.

1.5.1. To researcher

The outcome of this research helped the researcher to be experienced in doing the research. Indeed, it this work stands as partial fulfillment for the requirement of an award of Bachelor degree in Economics and Management.

1.5.2. To Rwandan government

The findings of this study are of great importance to the Rwandan government as policy makers as they will be able to design policies that could enhance accountability in integrating PAC recommendations in local administrative entities daily operations to ensure the effective performance of local administrative entities.

1.5.3. To Education sector

The study is of interest to students, professionals and researchers, as it will form the basis for more in depth studies with respect to implementation recommendation of PAC in local administrative entities operations. In the same way, this study will be a tool of reference for other researches who are interested in the same field of research.

1.5.4. To K.P

This study will be of great significance to KP since it will be a site of research documents for the other scholars who are interested in finding references in the same field. Likewise, it will be the

opportunity of showing how much the skills from KP are utilized in carrying out researches in the fields which are utmost important in performance of administrative entities.

1.6. LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

While carrying out this research different limitations could be encountered. In fact, the researcher could meet a problem of complicated subjects who could not want to cooperate with researcher, as they are biased, likely others do not want to give their information due to aggressiveness and suspicious of consequences relating to information they give, not only these limitations, also some of respondents could ask for money so that they can give information; and this was not provided in the budget of this research, hence causing lack of adequate information to facilitate primary data.

To overcome these challenges the researcher have to show how much this research is important to them and their generations then after they do accept to give reliable information. Additionally, the researcher have to ensure to respondent confidentiality and anonymity.

1.7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

1.7.1. Time scope

The study covered the period between 2015 and 2018.

1.7.2. Field scope

This study interested on assessing the contribution of PAC as a tool in improving performance of local administrative entities.

1.7.3. Space scope

This study took place in Nyamasheke district of Western province.

1.8. THESIS ORGANIZATION

The study is organized into five chapters. The first chapter is introduction highlighting the background to the study, statement of the problem, purpose of the study, research objectives, research questions, and significance of the study, limitations, thesis organization and scope of the study. Chapter two dwells on the review of related literature. The review is under different sub-topics which were guided by the research objectives. The chapter presents theoretical, empirical and conceptual framework of the study. The third chapter is on research methodology which covers research design, target population, sample size and sampling procedures, data collection process, validity of instruments and reliability of instruments and data analysis techniques. Chapter four

presents the data analysis, interpretation and discussions. Chapter five which is the last chapter focuses on the summary, conclusions, recommendations and suggestions for further studies have also been presented.

SUMMARY

This chapter presented the background of study where the problem under study was discussed on global, Africa and national level. It was of great importance to state the problem so to be able to set objectives which would be followed while carrying out the study. The objectives helped to set research questions which were used to set the questionnaire. In following step, the researcher showed the significance of this study in diverse carriers; additionally, the limitations met in this study were identified and finally scope and thesis organization were discussed.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0. INTRODUCTION

This chapter reviews the existing literature, information and publication on the topic related to the research problem by accredited scholars and researchers. This section shall examine what various scholars and authors have said about implementation PAC recommendation, in particular it covers the theoretical review of literature, conceptualization of the research problem empirical review of the literature and critical review and research gaps.

2.1. DEFINITION OF KEY CONCEPTS

2.1.1. Public accounts committee (PAC)

Public Accounts Committee (PAC) refers to a committee in the legislature that must study public audits, invite ministers, permanent secretaries or other ministry officials to the committee for questioning, and issue a report of their findings subsequent to a government budget audit.

(en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_Accounts_Committee)

A committee of considerable power who examines the auditors' reports to make sure that any government funding to the various departments of government is used in the correct manner and according to the government guidelines.

(thelawdictionary.org/public-accounts-committee-pac/)

2.1.2. Local administrative entities

Local administrative entity is a low level administrative division of a country, ranked below a province, region, or state. Not all countries describe their locally governed areas this way, but it can be descriptively applied anywhere to refer to counties, municipalities, etc.

(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Local_administrative_unit)

2.1.2. Performance

Performance is synonymous with organizational effectiveness, and it uses the following as criteria of evaluating performance: productivity, conformity, institutionalizing (Price, 1968).

Sustains that performance is a subjective and relative notion, mentioning six indicators which highlight the company performance: growth of the added value, return on engaged capitals, growth of fixed assets, changes in the workforce, covering the operating needs from the working capital, appointed liability compared with self-financing capacity. Performance is the accomplishment of a given task measured against preset known standards of accuracy, completeness, cost, and speed (Klein, 1976).

In a contract, performance is deemed to be the fulfillment of an obligation, in a manner that releases the performer from all liabilities under the contract.

According to Merriam Webster (2014) performance can be defined as the fulfillment of a claim, promise, or request.

2.1. Theoretical framework

2.1.1. Public Choice Theory and Organizational Practices

The behavior of the PAC in dealing with its functions may have its roots in public choice theory and organizational practice. The PAC's appointment commences with the process of when a group of individuals win the election, and subsequently appointed as members of the SLA, with the majority winning party forming the government. Members of the SLA, whether from the ruling party or the opposition, may be appointed to sit on committees such as PAC. Some of the questions that come to mind are firstly, whether those elected and later appointed, delegated and trusted to administer and make decisions on behalf of the nation are competent, and secondly, whether an effective system of oversight and sanctions can be established for such individuals as a check and balance of their work. The rights that have been reserved for the general public to impose oversight function on the state government in avoidance of harm due to misuse of power and misconduct that may exist of government officials, must be reserved (Mueller, 1989; Besley, 2007).

According to Allen et al. (1979), politics is an important behavioral process in organizational settings and the PAC is no exception. Under the public choice theory, the behavior of PAC members is presumed to be at two extremes, firstly, they are self-interested utility maximizers, motivated by factors like patronage, power, public reputation, and salaries. Secondly, PAC members may also be characterized as individuals who will work in the public interest; ensuring that laws and practice passed at SLA are working; having pride in their performance; and also

wishing to best serve the public (Allen, 1979; Besley, 2007). Hence, balancing their behavior along these two extremes will be a challenge to all PAC members.

2.1.2. Conventional wisdom theory

Conventional wisdom suggests that a strong legislature is built on a strong internal committee system, both in terms of committee powers and the willingness of members to engage in committee work. Committee assignments are the behavioral manifestation of legislative organization. Despite this, much remains unknown about how committee assignments happen and with what causes and consequences.

2.1.3. Agency theory

Currently, there is a trend to enhance legislative involvement in the budget process in line with the postulation of agency theory. According to the proponents of agency theory, the principal should be able to hold the agent accountable. In the context of this research, the legislature represents the citizens' interests and therefore hold the government accountable for all public financial dealings. Being the representative of the citizens, the legislature carries out its works through various committees of national or state assembly. One of these committees is the PAC.

2.2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Independent variable

Dependent Variable

In this chapter, the researcher had an interest in analyzing the correlation between independent variable and dependent variable which both were supported by control variable.

In fact, the researcher considered and analyzed the independent variable which was public accounts committee putting into consideration recommendations and follow up raised by PAC in Nyamasheke district.

Normally, in recommendation, this study concentrated on how PAC take care about financial matters, compliance matters, value for money matters whereas to follow up, the researcher put in place to investigate how PAC follow ups are done; Monthly PFM meeting, quarterly review of financial statement, quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning.

Regarding independent variable which performance of local administrative, this study evaluated the frequency attending PAC, Audit opinion and how the implementation of agreed actions is executed in local administrative entities of Nyamasheke district.

For control variables it was revealed that public financial and procurement management laws and regulations will help in giving the image of how the local administrative entities implemented PAC's recommendation through their performance.

2.2.1. RECOMMENDATION RAISED BY PAC

2.2.1.1. Financial matters

Financial matter include any matter relating to the institution's financial or property affairs. It includes any legal matter that relates to the financial or property affairs of the institution.

Some of example of financial matters could be:

- making money available to the institution for the institution's personal expenditure
- paying expenses for the institution and any dependents of the institution relating to the maintenance and accommodation of the institution and any dependents, including purchasing an interest in, or making a contribution to an establishment to accommodate the institution or any dependents of the institution or otherwise making payments in relation to such property
- paying any debts of the institution, including any fees and expenses to which an attorney is legally entitled;
- receiving and recovering money payable to the institution
- carrying on any trade or business of the institution
- performing any contracts entered into by the institution
- discharging any mortgage over the institution 's property
- paying rates, taxes and insurance premiums or other outgoings for the institution 's property
- insuring the principal or the institution 's property
- otherwise preserving or improving the institution 's property
- making investments for the institution

- continuing investments of the institution, including taking up rights to issues of new shares, or options for new shares to which the principal becomes entitled by the institution 's existing shareholding
- undertaking any real estate transaction for the institution
- dealing with land for the institution
- Undertaking a beneficial transaction for the principal involving the use of the institution's property as security for an obligation, including taking out a loan on behalf of the institution or giving a guarantee on behalf of the institution.
- Withdrawing money from or depositing money into an account of the institution with a financial institution.

2.2.1.2. Compliance matters

Today security and compliance teams are faced with a plethora of security standards and regulatory obligations. While standards typically provide recommended guidance, regulations are mandatory and must be addressed. Noncompliance can lead to fines and penalties, and even worse, potential damage to the organization's reputation. For these reasons and more, compliance does indeed matter.

If individual organizations are left alone to determine appropriate levels of security, this leads to dramatic variation in security from organization to organization. Potentially, this leaves those organizations, and anyone who works with them, more vulnerable. The creation of standards and regulatory requirements leverages the knowledge and expertise of the greater security industry to provide a common security baseline.

Implementing this baseline across organizations enables standardization and uniformity within the organization, and promotes accountability among both organizations and individuals. Further, today compliance means more than meeting the requirements of a one-time or periodic audit. The compliance environment has evolved to require organizations to demonstrate ongoing attainment of the minimum standard of performance. Doing this manually would be an impossible task. Continuous compliance monitoring enables organizations to know what is going on across the network in near-real time, and ensure alignment with required regulations. Continuous compliance matters not because of standards, but because our businesses are in a constant state of flux. If we

want to increase our chances of preventing security exposures, we must embrace compliance and embed it into our business practices.

Normally, Compliance Matters refer to any Law to which Seller, the Business or the Assets may be subject on or prior to the Closing.

For example, the Sub-Advisor shall provide to the Trust CCO: (i) quarterly reports confirming the Sub-Advisor's compliance with the Sub-Advisor Compliance Procedures in managing the Sub-Advisor Assets, and (ii) certifications indicating whether there were Material Compliance Matters involving the Sub-Advisor that arose under the Sub-Advisor Compliance Procedures that affected the Sub-Advisor Assets. Access Persons may submit a complaint, report or concern regarding accounting, internal accounting controls, auditing matters or potential/actual violations of applicable laws, rules, regulations or internal policies and procedures, including this Code (collectively, "Compliance Matters"), without fear of dismissal or retaliation of any kind. Any Access Person may submit a report regarding Compliance Matters on a confidential or anonymous basis by: calling the Compliance Director or, in their absence, the General Counsel; or * writing to the Compliance Director or, in their absence, the General Counsel via email or regular mail. The Reserve prohibits retaliation against any Access Person who makes a report regarding Compliance Matters or who participates in any investigation.

2.2.1.3. Value for money matters

Value for money audit, according to Okwoli (2004) is “a systematic evaluation of the methodologies employed in the execution of programs, projects, and activities with the objectives of confirming whether the stated objectives of the programs, projects, and activities were actually achieved and at what cost”. According to him, this method of audit has evolved over time and been found to be the best approach to confirming whether managers of resources are applying best practices in the use and application of resources.

Value for money audit has been found to be particularly useful in public sector where measurement of results achieved by public sector organizations is more subjective than in the private sector. In the private sector, measurement of the success of an enterprise is a function of the profit of such an enterprise. Its continuous existence depends entirely on the ability of the enterprises to make profit without which it will fold up. Whereas the private sector enterprises Endeavour to make

profit in order to continue to remain in business. This particular urge is not very prevalent in public sector. Public sector enterprises are set up specifically to address various problems, some social, while some are economic. However, profit motive is not usually the main objective of setting up such bodies. Even though many of such enterprises are not strictly set up as profit-making organizations, it is expected that they should not contribute an undue burden to the Government.

2.2.2. FOLLOW UP OF THE RECOMMENDATIONS RAISED BY PAC

The finalization of a report by the committee should not be the end of the PAC process. Reports only have practical value if the government addresses the issues it raises, and implements the recommendations of the committee. In practice, while experiences vary, the Treasury Minute is not always a satisfactory mechanism for ensuring that the committee's recommendations are acted upon. The responses it contains may not always be very specific, and it can be difficult, given parliament's often-limited resources, to ensure independently that sufficient action was taken by the government to address particular concerns of the PAC (Blöndal, 2001) .

Some countries go further in their follow-up through the use of a formal tracking report produced regularly by the audit institution. Tabled at a later stage, for instance two years after an initial audit report, it systematically considers the extent of implementation of each set of recommendations adopted by the committee. Rather than a separate tracking report, some auditor general's follow a process whereby they include a review of departmental action on previous recommendations in an annual audit report. In addition, with regard to particularly important issues, it might be useful to consider interim reporting requirements to ensure that the government takes remedial action as speedily as possible. This might take the form of periodic briefings of the committee by relevant officials (Burnell, 2001).

In fact, this follow up must be done by referring to; monthly PFM meeting, quarterly review of financial statement, quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning

Empirically, Value For Money (VFM) examinations are potentially more far reaching as a means of audit. Section 6 of the 1983 Act provides a statutory basis for VFM examinations at the discretion of the C & AG. Included within this jurisdiction are government departments and other public bodies where the C & AG has statutory rights of inspection or where he is the statutory auditor. VFM audit is not extended to the nationalized industries. For many years the Committee of Public Accounts (PAC) encouraged the C & AG to examine expenditure and receipts in

departments and to bring to the notice of Parliament weakness of the system which appeared 'to involve imprudent, uneconomical or extravagant expenditure of waste'. The 1983 Act placed such examinations on a statutory basis. However the Act makes an important proviso that VFM examination shall not be construed as entitling the C & AG to question the merits of the policy objectives of the department or body concerned (C. Beauchamp.,1990).

2.2.2.1. Monthly PFM meeting

The PFM Reform strategy focuses on building human resource capacity, putting in place modern and effective systems and procedures for effective financial management and reporting and strengthening the institutional framework in accordance with international best practices for a more efficient and transparent PFM system.

For instance in Rwanda; it also aims at increasing effective coordination of various reforms, sequencing the reforms to the priorities of the country consistent with both the Economic Development and Poverty Reduction Strategy (EDPRS) and the Vision 2020, and to ensure effective implementation.

Subsequent to the establishment of the MINECOFIN Single Project Implementation Unit, the Public Financial Management Reform Portfolio will continue with its central role of increasing the pace of reforms and to coordinate effectively the PFM reform agenda.

Key functions include the following
(www.minecofin.gov.rw/fileadmin/templates/.../Public_Financial_Management.pdf)

- Facilitating meetings of the PFM Reform Steering Committee, PFM Reform Technical Committee and ensuring that Component Leaders conduct periodic meetings of the Component Working Teams;
- Providing technical support and guidance to the PFM Reform program with emphasis on effective delivery and longer-term sustainability;
- Supporting Pillar leaders and component leaders to develop annual action plans and budgets within the framework of the PFM Reform Strategy and ensure that they are reviewed and approved;
- Ensuring that budgets and procurement plans are prepared and approved;
- Sequencing reforms under various components through component leaders;

- Ensuring that the M&E System to track the implementation of the PFM Reform Strategy on a regular basis is developed and providing support in monitoring the implementation of PFM Reforms;
- Reviewing technical aspects of all consultancy terms of reference to ensure proper alignment to the PFM objectives under the PFM reform strategy;
- Advising on and providing technical support to the pillar leaders and component leaders in building their capacity to ensure their increased understanding and mastery of the technical and change management aspects of PFM reforms for greater ownership and sustainability of the PFM reforms program;
- Providing technical backstopping to all the ongoing PFM consultancies;
- Ensuring that reforms are on track to achieve the objectives and targets envisaged in the PFM Reform Strategy.

2.2.2.2. Public Financial and Procurement management laws and regulations

Central Government Budget Law is the Law that indicates the revenue and expenditure estimations of the public administrations included in the central government and that grants authority and permission for their realization and implementation.

Central Government Budget Law should include revenue and expenditure estimations of the first year and following two years; budget deficit or surplus amount, how the deficit will be covered or where the surplus will be used if any; tax revenues renounced due to tax exemptions, exceptions, reductions and similar practices; borrowing and warranty limits; authorities to be granted for the implementation of budgets; relevant schedules and provisions, pertaining to revenues and expenditures, to be totally or partially implemented or not to be implemented at all during the fiscal year. The revenue-expenditure estimations of each public administration within the scope of central government may be presented in special sections or schedules of the Central Government Budget Law.

Likewise, effecting expenditures from budgets is pending to the delivery of a spending instruction issued by the authorizing officer. The spending instruction shall include information on the statement of the purpose of service as well as subject, amount, duration, available appropriation and realization procedure of the work to be performed and on realization officers.

Authorizing officers are responsible for the compliance of spending instructions with the budget principles and basics, laws, by-laws and regulations and other legislations, for the effective, economic and efficient utilization of the appropriations and for other transactions they shall perform in the framework of this Law.

2.2.3. OVERVIEW OF PUBLIC ACCOUNTS COMMITTEE (PAC)

2.2.3.1. Introduction

The PAC works effectively when it:

- ✓ is appropriately sized, involving members from across parliamentary parties reflecting the make-up of the legislature or includes non-members of the House with acknowledged relevant expertise;
- ✓ is chaired by a member from an opposition party or non-member of the House to increase public confidence in scrutiny of government;
- ✓ works with a non-partisan culture focusing on financial management improvement to benefit citizen and taxpayer;
- ✓ preferably holds meetings open to the public and the media, with all documentation published soon after the meeting;
- ✓ publishes reports and recommendations which are easy for the public and the general reader to understand and which require a written response from government;
- ✓ maintains active and constructive relationships with the SAI;
- ✓ has access to appropriate support from parliamentary staff;
- ✓ engages in a balanced manner with the media to increase public awareness of PAC role and work.

2.2.3.2. Audit opinion and PAC

In a government audit, an auditor determines whether the financial statements of an entity are presented fairly in all material respects and in accordance with accounting standards by reviewing the underlying information and processes that went into preparing the financial statements. Audit reports include an opinion as to whether there is a reasonable assurance that the financial statements are free from material misstatements.

Audit opinions are divided into three type; unmodified, multiple and modified opinions. Among unmodified opinion; the auditor concludes that the financial statements of a given entity are

presented fairly, in all material respects, in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles.

Multiple opinions occur when the auditor expresses different opinions on various aspects of the financial statements.

Modified opinions include; qualified opinion, an adverse opinion, or a disclaimer of opinion.

Through qualified opinion The auditor, having obtained sufficient appropriate audit evidence, concludes that misstatements, individually or in the aggregate, are material but not pervasive to the financial statements, or the auditor is unable to obtain sufficient appropriate audit evidence on which to base the opinion, but concludes that the possible effects on the financial statements of undetected misstatements, if any, could be material but not pervasive.

Adverse opinion are identified after having obtained enough good audit evidence, the auditor concludes that misstatements, individually or when grouped with other misstatements, are both material and pervasive to the financial statements.

In disclaimer of Opinion the auditor is unable to obtain sufficient appropriate audit evidence on which to base the opinion, and concludes that the possible effects on the financial statements of undetected misstatements, if any, could be both material and pervasive.

Public Accounts Committee (PAC) refers to a committee in the legislature that must study public audits, invite ministers, permanent secretaries or other ministry officials to the committee for questioning, and issue a report of their findings subsequent to a government budget audit. Typically, the government is required to report back to parliament on PAC recommendations within a specified period, usually two to six months. More often than not, opposition members chair PACs in the commonwealth. Based on their findings, PACs often make recommendations to government ministries requiring that they change certain policies and procedures to improve their operations.

The majority of legislatures descending from the British Parliament use public account committees to follow up on the findings of public audits. Since the creation of the Public Accounts Committee in the Gladstonian Reforms of 1861, PACs have become ubiquitous throughout the Commonwealth. The tremendous expansion and scope of government and of state-owned enterprises during the second half of the 20th century made PACs, which are charged with overseeing government expenditures, even more important.

Public Accounts Committees face several challenges. For one, auditors general are often poorly funded, and their reports may be lengthy, complex, poorly organized, and difficult to understand. Funding and staff shortages mean that audit reports are often years behind, so ministry officials needed for questioning might have moved on. In many cases auditors general are appointed by the executive and so may have little incentive to uncover problems that could embarrass those who appointed them. Investigating report findings is time and labor-intensive. Parliaments need professional staff, but they are often not available. Finally, governments are often not responsive to parliament, and there may be few tools at a parliament's disposal to compel government compliance.

2.2.3.3. Implementation of agreed actions

Public accounts committees (PACs) are tasked with scrutinizing executive use of public money, undertaking inquiries with the support of the legislative auditor. Through several means, an expectation is placed on members to be politically neutral in undertaking committee work. However, in the context of Northern Ireland, where consociationalism entrenches binary ethno-national identities throughout the political institutions, it would be expected that party-political interests would prevail and fracture the committee.

Public Accounts Committees (PACs) fundamentally demand non-partisanship in their work (O'Dea, 2015). Achieving an apolitical approach to committee work is challenging in any legislature, however, for example in Northern Ireland, partisanship along community lines is instilled throughout the institutions as a result of consociationalism. The historical and deep-seated nature of the division in Northern Ireland means that working across designated groupings within the Assembly and across parties is a much more difficult task than might be typical in more traditional left-right political settings. PAC members are, therefore, placed in a difficult position, where their committee demands an apolitical stance in their work, and their position as an elected representative requires a clear identification as 'Nationalist', 'Unionist' or 'Other' in addition to their party affiliation, clearly demarcating and emphasizing the differences between these individuals.

The duty of PAC of both chambers is to examine the accounts showing the appropriation of the sums granted by the National Assembly to meet the public expenditure together with the Auditor's

report thereon. Basically each house established its own PAC but performs the same function and are meant to double check and lay emphasis on fiscal accountability of public funds (NASS, 2012).

Senate PAC: The Order XIII Rule 97(5) of the Senate Standing Orders 2007 as amended states that there shall be a Committee to be known as Public Accounts Committee appointed at the commencement of the life of the Senate. The jurisdiction of the committee shall include: (a) to examine the accounts showing the appropriation of the sums granted by the Senate to meet the public expenditure; together with the Auditor's report thereon. The Committee shall, for the purposes of discharging that duty, have power to send for any person, papers and records, to report from time to time to the Senate and to sit notwithstanding the adjournment of the Senate; (b) the Committee shall have power to examine any accounts or report of statutory Corporations and Boards after they have been laid on the table for the Senate and to report thereon from time to time to the Senate and to sit notwithstanding the adjournment of the Senate; (c) the Committee shall have power to enquire the report of the Auditor-General of the Federation with respect to any prepayment audit query which had been overruled by the Chief Executive of the Ministry, Extra-Ministerial Departments or Agency of the Federal Government and Courts of the Federation and to report same to the Senate.

House of Representative PAC: Order XVII Rule A.6. (1) Of the House Standing Orders states that there shall be a Committee to be known as the Public Accounts Committee consisting of not more than 40 members appointed at the commencement of the life of the House. (2) The Committee's jurisdiction shall include: (a) to examine the accounts showing the appropriation of the sums granted by the House to meet the Public expenditure, together with the auditor's reports thereon. (b) Have power to summon persons, summon papers and records, and report its findings and recommendations to the House from time to time. (3) The Auditor-General shall bring to the attention of the Committee any pre-payment audit queries raised by the Internal Auditors of a Ministry, Department or Agency but over ruled by the Chief Executive. (4) The Public Accounts Committee shall have the power to examine any accounts or reports of statutory corporations and Board after they shall have been laid on the Table of the House and to report thereon from time to time to the House.

2.2.4. RECOMMENDATIONS RAISED BY PAC AND OFFICE OF AUDITOR GENERAL (OAG)

The process of financial scrutiny is based on collecting evidence on the appropriateness of government plans or actions, and communicating conclusions and any recommendations for improvement to Parliament and the public. Committees will generally collect evidence in the following ways:

- ✓ question government officials, suppliers, contractors and/or advisors at public meetings;
- ✓ question independent experts from universities, business or non-governmental organizations at public meetings;
- ✓ request and review written submissions from government or independent experts; and
- ✓ place reliance on reports produced by the Supreme Audit Institution (SAI)

Based on this work the Committee will usually produce a report containing its conclusions on the issues examined. The objective for post-expenditure scrutiny is to recommend changes and improvements that will prevent past problems recurring in future.

While PACs will differ in their structure, there are a number of shared characteristics contributing to effectiveness and impact. These typically blend formal powers and informal ways of working.

Effective financial oversight committees:

- ✓ focus on the management of public finances not policy, endeavouring to gain consensus on behalf of the taxpayer and citizen rather than on purely party-political considerations;
- ✓ call officials (on rare occasions only, ministers), suppliers, contractors and advisers as appropriate for constructive questioning relating to public expenditure;
- ✓ demand relevant documents to the inquiry, or rely on the independent audit of such documents mainly by the SAI;
- ✓ report directly to the legislature; and
- ✓ make recommendations to which government must formally and publicly respond.

2.2.4.1. Recommendation on financial matters

Governments are accountable to the legislature for the way they spend the money they raise from taxpayers and elsewhere. Before money is spent, legislatures will approve government income and expenditure plans. After the money has been spent legislatures should demand assurance that the money has been spent in accordance with those plans in a way likely to achieve value for money,

and should seek explanations and improvements when things have gone wrong. Post-expenditure scrutiny forms the heart of constructive Parliamentary Accounts Committee (PAC) work.

Structures for undertaking parliamentary financial scrutiny may vary in line with respective constitutions. Many share similar features, in particular:

- ✓ a legislature which requires the government to prepare income and expenditure plans (budgets) specifying how much money they intend to raise and how it will be spent;
- ✓ government ministries and other agencies which prepare accounts and related reports showing how the money was spent against the budget;
- ✓ an independent Supreme Audit Institution (SAI) which audits these accounts and reports to the legislature;
- ✓ a PAC within the legislature considers work undertaken by the SAI, makes recommendations to government, considers government responses and reports to the legislature

In addition some countries have:

- ✓ civil society organizations which review government action and provide expertise and insight from outside the legislative process; and
- ✓ the media

Undertaking financial scrutiny is challenging as public finance documents are often technical and contain a high volume of information. It is also a challenge for members of parliament to balance the demands of financial scrutiny alongside their other roles and responsibilities in the legislature. The process of financial scrutiny can at times be intensely political. In dealing with the SAI's reports the PAC should focus on improving the administration of public funds and not challenge government policies. Using these hearings and reports as a way of embarrassing a government and attacking ministerial decisions undermines the value and credibility of the PAC.

Parliaments expect governments to report back to them on how they spent the money allocated to them when the expenditure plan was approved. This is usually in the form of annual accounts.

Timetables for the production of financial reports will usually be set out in law or regulations.

PACs will scrutinize accounts in order to check a range of risks to taxpayers' money including:

- ✓ the organization spending more than expected;
- ✓ the organization becoming less financially efficient; and

- ✓ examples of waste, fraud or contentious payments

Serious problems with the legality and compliance of spending will usually be highlighted in the Supreme Audit Institute (SAI)'s report on the accounts. Given the volume audited by an SAI, it is important that a PAC prioritizes its efforts focusing on the major problems emerging from the audits. Minor issues should be handled directly between the SAI and the relevant Ministry or Agency.

Effective financial oversight committees:

- ✓ focus on the management of public finances not policy, endeavouring to gain consensus on behalf of the taxpayer and citizen rather than on purely party-political considerations;
- ✓ call officials (on rare occasions only, ministers), suppliers, contractors and advisers as appropriate for constructive questioning relating to public expenditure;
- ✓ demand relevant documents to the inquiry, or rely on the independent audit of such documents mainly by the SAI;
- ✓ report directly to the legislature; and
- ✓ Make recommendations to which government must formally and publicly respond.

2.4.4.2. Recommendations on compliance matters

Scrutiny of financial reports can highlight issues around financial performance. It does not provide parliament or the public with a view of the outputs achieved with the money granted to government. While the accounts may show expenditure increasing, judgment on efficiency and effectiveness can only really be made when the PAC has evidenced information on the extent to which outputs and productivity have increased too. Scrutiny of performance is therefore necessary alongside scrutiny of accounts in order to identify risks such as: Government delivering less output than expected; Government delivering lower quality output than expected; and Government delivering output to different beneficiaries than expected

2.2.4.3. Recommendations on value for monetary matters

The National audit office (NAO) has developed Value for Money (VFM) strategies that emphasize the avoidance of waste, the setting of clearly defined policy objectives, and obtaining good value for the tax-payers. There is a duty on government departments to consider the NAO's reports and the PAC recommendations, and to provide replies to the House of Commons on matters raised in

the reports. VFM examinations seem to be a blend of conventional auditing skills with management consulting techniques. In the former they benefit from a degree of independence and objectivity and the ascertaining of facts through the skills of an auditor. It is clear that the latter draws on the analytical skills of the management consultant and the practical skills of the accountant. In comparison with ordinary certification auditing VFM takes the opportunity to understand the effects of policy and whether those effects relate to the intention behind the policy. The NAO's experience of VFM has increased markedly given the large number of VFM studies since 1983 (NAO, 1999).

Particularly difficult to categorize is the distinction to be drawn between the implementation of policy, a legitimate concern of VFM, and the merits of policy which is outside the jurisdiction of the NAO. A criticism levied at all public sector VFM examinations is that the emphasis on economic criteria may not take account of political choices and policy-making or whether the merits of the policy, outside the remit of the NAO, impacted on the efficiency of the decision making.

2.2.5. PROGRESSIVE IMPLEMENTATION OF PAC AND OAG RECOMMENDATIONS

The PAC occupies an important formal position as an institution of accountability charged with undertaking the legislature's scrutiny and oversight processes over the use of public sector resources by government. In line with the provisions of Article 103, the PAC was established by Order 151(2) of the Standing Orders of Parliament of Ghana to examine the audited accounts of government showing sums granted by parliament to meet public expenditure and use. The PACs assist the process of public audit and at the same time help to achieve the parliamentary objective of ensuring that government is held accountable on behalf of the electorate, in particular for its use of public money.

The primary function of the PAC according to Standing Order 165(2) is to critically “examine the audited accounts showing the appropriation of the sums granted by Parliament to meet the public expenditure of the government and such other accounts laid before parliament”. This singular function of the PAC positions it at the intersection between public audit and parliamentary accountability.

Traditionally it has been the mandate of the Auditor General's Office (AG) through Article 187(2) of the 1992 constitution to “audit all the public accounts of Ghana and of all public offices, including the courts, the central and local government administration of the Universities and the public institutions of like nature of any public cooperation or other body or organization established by Act of parliament”.

Furthermore, section 5 of Article 187 requires the Auditor General to forward the audited accounts to Parliament which is then referred to the PAC of the House by the speaker. The PAC is thus positioned at the intersection between public audit and parliamentary accountability. McGee (2002) argues that effectively linking the audit process with parliament scrutiny and oversight is essential for transparency and accountability in government spending. Thus, the PAC commences its ex-post financial scrutiny by examining and acting upon a report from AG's office. In most cases public hearings and written responses to queries are the principal mechanisms by which officials from departments, agencies and other relevant bodies answer to the PAC.

The purpose of these public hearings is to add value to the audit report through summoning and questioning of witnesses publicly and to inform the citizenry of mechanisms to hold public officials to account, in particular for its use of public money through their representatives in parliament. The rationale for conducting hearings publicly is that transparency and accountability become mutually reinforcing objectives.

After thorough consideration and scrutiny of the Auditor General's report, the PAC issues a report and recommendations which are deliberated on the floor of the House. As part of the execution of its duty, the PAC has the mandate to recommend to the appropriate authorities actions or sanctions that can be taken against public officials who may be found culpable of any offences relating to financial malfeasance.

It is important to note that, the debate of a PAC report on the findings of the AG by the legislature should not be construed as the end of the ex-post scrutiny process. There is the need to implement the PAC recommendations and periodically follow-up to verify the status of recommendations outlined in the report. McGee (2002) writes that devising effective follow-up mechanisms is very important for parliament to ensure that audit findings and any recommendations are actually implemented to improve public expenditure and administration in general.

Audit Report Implementation Committees (ARICs) to pursue the implementation of matters in all audit reports endorsed by parliament as well as financial matters raised in the reports of the internal monitoring unit. Furthermore, the ARICs are also mandated to prepare annual statements showing the status of the implementation of recommendation made in all audit reports as well as the AG's report which has been accepted by Parliament and any other related directives from Parliament. The ARICs are to forward the statement on the status report endorsed by the relevant Minister and forwarded to Parliament, Office of the President and the Auditor General within six months after parliamentary decisions on the AG's report.

On the other hand, there is also a financial tribunal established under the Financial Administration Act clause 64 to complement the work of the ARICs by enforcing recommendations of the PAC on the Auditor General's report as approved by parliament. Recently, concerns have been raised over the practical value of these PAC recommendations and the effectiveness of ARICs in checking corruption in public spending due to the reoccurrence of misappropriation of public funds in successive AG reports. Kan-Dapaah (2011) reinforces this argument by acknowledging the non-existence of key institutions to follow up on PAC recommendations especially issues that bother on corruption. Some commentators on the operations of the PAC in Ghana argue that the work of the committee does not go beyond inspection of records and supervising the activities of the Auditor General (Kafui, 2011).

2.2.6. PAC AND PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE ENTITIES

Under the PMFL the Auditor General is provided with a clear mandate to undertake performance and public interest audits. The PMFL states that the Auditor General on his own initiative or at the request of the Legislative Assembly or of any of its committees or subcommittees can conduct investigations and value for money audits, into:

- the management of executive financial transactions;
- the financial management of any ministry, portfolio, statutory authority or government company or the Office of the Complaints Commissioner; or the Office of the Information Commissioner; and
- the economy, efficiency and effectiveness with which any ministry, portfolio, the Office of the Complaints Commissioner, the Office of the Information Commissioner, or any statutory authority

or government company has used its resources in discharging its functions and in its financial dealings.

To meet this mandate the OAG carries out two types of audits: performance audits; and public interest audits. The results of this work are provided to the Legislative Assembly and are normally referred to the PAC where they are reviewed and considered for how the recommendations could improve government operations.

Regarding performance audits (previously called value-for-money audits); performance audits are based on a planned and published program of work, covering efficiency, effectiveness, economy, governance and accountability, and are conducted following the International Standards for Auditing. Our current performance audit program was published in January 2015 and details the performance audits that we are planning to undertake for the period 2015 - 2017. In addition it provides information on other topics on which we plan to keep a watching brief and may audit in the future. Click on the following link for a copy of our current program.

Public interest audits are focused on important issues identified during the year, and which in the public interest, should be reported to the Legislative Assembly in as short a time frame as possible. In general these are reactive, will cover single issues at an individual entity. To an extent they draw on issues identified through our audit of the financial statements, but are also the result of issues of public interest that are brought to our attention.

Empirically, in the study carried out by Lord Sharman's Report, *Holding to Account: The Review of Audit and Accountability for Central Government* (2001) argued that public money should receive greater scrutiny than private money and advocated a broader definition of public money. He also noted that the PAC was often criticized for failing to encourage innovation and risk taking. However, there were no specific examples that illustrated this criticism. This leaves the suspicion that the PAC may have become over complacent in its role.

Additionally, The National Audit Act 1983 recognized the constitutional implications of the office of C&AG and made the C & AG an Officer of the House of Commons and provided for his appointment. As head of the National Audit Office (NAO), which was created under the 1983 Act and replaced the Exchequer and Audit Department, the C & AG is independent from both politics

and political influence of the government of the day. This independence allows the C&AG to qualify financial accounts when he is not satisfied of the financial arrangements. In November 2002 this occurred over the Strategic Rail Authority sponsored by the Department of Transport until it was agreed that Network Rail should be consolidated back into full public ownership. Public ownership came about because of systemic failures in the maintenance of track and the quality control over repairs. Prior to privatization British Rail, a nationalized industry had responsibility for operating an integrated railway system involving track maintenance and train operations.

The NAO claims in its Annual Report that through efficiency savings there are substantial gains to the Treasury. In the past three years, the NAO claims that it saves the taxpayer an average of £512 million per annum. These savings arise through the close cooperation between the NAO and the PAC. The PAC benefits from the NAO's expertise and the power to refer matters back to the NAO provides a means to monitor and follow-up on the work of government. In addition the NAO provides the PAC with substantial briefing in preparation for the taking of oral evidence in public. This use of specialized analysis is a major reason for the PAC's potency. Departmental permanent secretaries attend PAC meetings and Chief

Executives of Agencies and their Accounting Officers are also in attendance. On average the PAC annually produces over 50 reports. As A. Brazier notes: According to the NAO, the government responds to about 1,000 recommendations from the PAC in an average Parliament, and accepts about 95% of them (A. Brazier, 2006). The work load of the PAC is therefore greater than any other select committee.

The power of enforcing the AG'S report is vested in the National Assembly through PAC. Recently some of the audit findings includes: Over-invoicing, non-retirement of cash advances, lack of internal audit inspection, payment for jobs not done, double-debiting, contract inflation, lack of supporting documents to back up various purchases, shameless violation of financial regulations, and release of money without the approving authority's involvement (Emenyonu, 2007). All these are disclosed in various AG's reports but without appropriate action and if there is any, at least not known to the public (Okpala, 2012b).

This practice of not resolving issues by PAC is against accountability and shows the existence of weak accounting infrastructure (regulations and oversight). PAC responsibility of examining the public accounts on the basis of the observations raised in the Auditor-General's report and ensuring that all issues highlighted therein are properly addressed has to best knowledge of Nigerians been neglected for many years. Its duty of acting as a mediator between the Accountant-General and the Auditor-General is also of no consequence.

2.3. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

In his study, Ogbanu (1991) about the role of PAC in performance of public funds use, where the objective was to evaluate the PAC influence on judiciousness of public funds use, he noted that PAC can enhance judiciousness in the disbursement of public funds by the public servants which will result in financial savings that can be channeled to the provision of amenities to improve the standard of living of Nigerians but have not been able to discharge its duties as expected; he recommended that PAC should be strengthened to ensure effective use of public funds.

On other hand, in the study carried out by Ibrahim UMAR (2017) on the performance and challenges of Public Accounts Committees (PAC) with main objective identify the effectiveness of PACs; the results showed that that lack of responsiveness from the government, the varying quality of audit reporting, the evolving nature of audit content, and the increased institutional complexity of government have hindered the effectiveness of the PAC in achieving its oversight functions. Furthermore, the proper functioning of the PAC is assumed to depend on certain factors including the committee size, presence of opposition chair and adequacy of supporting staff. He concluded that the performance of the PAC in Yobe State is below expectation. Specifically, there is delay in tabling the PAC report, the recommendation of the Committee is rarely implemented and there has never been any disciplinary action. Finally, he recommended that an increase in the membership of PAC, appointment of an opposition member to chair the PAC and the employ more supporting staff to handle the work of the PAC.

Broadbent and Laughlin (2005) maintain in their study entitled role of PAC on performance of public originations that organizations are not self-determining systems but they are linked into wider societal systems. Their results showed that the societal system provides the societally-defined purposes for organizations' existence. They concluded that the Federal Constitutions 1957

of Malaysia and the institutions namely legislative, executive and judiciary which it establishes tend to reflect these linkages. They recommended that PAC in particular are legislative organizations that have a degree of protection, they could not be abolished nor have their functions altered without the consent of Federal and State Constitutions.

2.6. SUMMARY

The second chapter described deeply all literatures from other author who were interested on the topic of this research. Actually, it was necessary to define all the key terms of the topic, and after literatures were organized by talking about theoretical review where all possible theories relating to the topic and objectives were cited, conceptual framework, empirical review and finally the chapter was summarized.

CHAPTER THREE: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0. INTRODUCTION

This chapter shows various methods which were used in this study. The chapter covers different used research approaches and the design of the study, within this chapter, it includes target population, sampling procedures, sample Size, data Collection process, reliability and validity of measurements and data analysis used while carrying out this study.

3.1. RESEARCH APPROCHES AND DESIGN

3.1.1. Research approaches

The present research put into consideration two approaches including: quantitative and qualitative.

3.1.1.1. Quantitative approach

This approach helped in describing numerical data to investigate situation in data collection.

3.1.1.2. Qualitative approach

This approach emphasizes on description where people's event views and arguments to give different ideas and arguments about the study.

The researcher uses this approach to collect different ideas relating to the problem under the study which could not be given in terms of frequencies.

3.1.2. Research design

The researcher used descriptive survey research design. The major aim of a descriptive study according to Kumar (2005) is to describe and provide information on what is prevalent regarding a group of people, a community, a phenomenon or a situation.

In order to achieve the objective of this study by providing information on effect of PAC on performance of local government entities, this study embarked on the research mission of using quantitative and qualitative methods to investigate a number of both variables.

This study showed the correlation between the independent research variables and dependent variable as well as how control variable influenced the previous relationship.

3.2. TARGET POPULATION

All the items under consideration in any field of inquiry constitute a universe or population. It can be presumed that in such an inquiry when all the items are covered no element of chance is left and highest accuracy is obtained (Kothari, 2004). The target population of this study was the members and the managing staff of Nyamasheke districts especially those who work closely with PAC and local administrative entities members where focused on Finance unit composed by 6 people, Auditing Committee of 5 people, Office of Audit composed by 2 Auditors, Executive Committee of 5 people, Procurement office of 2 people and District council committee of 3 people. In general targeted population will be of 23 people.

3.3. SAMPLING PROCEDURES

This survey was not able to study all members of the population. Concerning sampling technique, among Nyamasheke district staff managing board and some members of local administrative entities were considered and they received a questionnaire as targeted population by using stratified sampling procedure.

It is obvious that statistic analysis (linear regression) was applied as the study was descriptive. As a practical matter, researchers are seldom in a position to guarantee that every element meeting the theoretical definitions laid down actually has a chance of being selected in the sample (Creswell, J.W. (1994); Kothari, 1984; Babbie, 2008).

Slovin's formula allows a researcher to sample the population with a desired degree of accuracy. Slovin's formula was used to calculate the sample size.

The Slovin's formula is calculated as follows

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

Slovin (2013)

n= Number of samples or sample size

N= Total population

e= Error tolerance=0.1

3.4. SAMPLE SIZE

When it is not possible to study an entire population but the population is known, a smaller sample is taken using a random sampling technique.

One approach is to use the entire population as the sample. Although cost considerations make this impossible for large populations, a census is attractive for small populations (e.g., 200 or less). A census eliminates sampling error and provides data on all the individuals in the population (Glenn, D. I, 1992).

Therefore while carrying out this study the researcher considered 23 respondents who were target population by using census method for small population.

3.5. DATA COLLECTION PROCESS

While carrying out this study several research instruments were put in use including; documentation, questionnaire survey, interview guide and checklists were sources of information for supporting the results from gathered data.

They are two data collection sources: primary and secondary sources. Primary data were used to provide firsthand information relating to the subject under the study and secondary data are data collected from existing information that was compiled by others. In collecting secondary data the researcher used documentation methods in this data collection process that is based on reading text books and documents that gave the researcher several related literature on the research study.

In conducting this research study the required data were gathered from both primary and secondary data sources. The information required helped the researcher to achieve the set objectives.

3.5.1. Primary data

During the research, primary data were used to obtain from the sample elements relevant information concerning the whole people under the study. The technique used was questionnaire, interview and checklist. The questionnaire was addressed to the selected members of the staff of PAC and members of local administrative entities under the study and contained both close-ended and open-ended questions.

3.5.1.1. Questionnaire

The researcher use to design open and closed questions which were submitted to respondents; they answered on the same paper while giving their views and ideas. Afterwards the researcher collected the questionnaires to be interpreted and analyzed using SPSS version 18.0.

Interviewing may give information which might have been forgotten or failed to understand during answering the questionnaires.

3.5.1.2. Interview schedule

Interviewing refers to the gathering of data from respondents through interviews designed to capture required information from respondents.

The interviewee's own interpretation of events and issues must be considered and the researcher or interviewer has to pay attention, so he/she does not lose any valuable information, the interviewer may have and also not trying to constrain the interviewee's responses.

Interviewing may give information which might have been forgotten or failed to understand during answering the questionnaires.

This technique was used to collect the information from the respondents who were not able to respond to the questionnaire due to the matter of time and several duties, for instance the Executive committee and District council committee.

3.5.2. Secondary data

The sources of secondary data for this study were from the libraries and the documents from the office of Nyamasheke district which was taken as case study. Extensive study and review of published and unpublished documents, reports, journals, magazines and policy reports relevant to the study was done.

3.5.2.1. Documentation

According to Bailey (1982), this is the data collection method, which is based on reading textbooks and other documents.

Thus, various documents were consulted including; reports, textbooks and electronic journals.

3.6. RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY MEASUREMENTS

3.6.1 Reliability of research instruments

Reliability is the consistency of a set of measurement items while validity indicates that the instrument is testing what it should (Cronbach, 1951). Reliability is the consistency of your measurement, or the degree to which an instrument measures the same way each time it is used under the same condition with the same subjects. In short, it is the probability of your measurement. A measure is considered reliable if a person's score on the same test given twice is similar. It is important to remember that reliability is not measured, it is estimated. Reliability does not, however, imply validity because while scale may be measuring something consistently, it may not necessarily be what it is supposed to be measuring. The researcher will use the most common internal consistency measure known as Cronbach's alpha (α). It indicates the extent to which a set of test items can be treated as measuring a single latent variable (Cronbach, 1951).

There commended value of 0.7 will be used as a cut-off of reliabilities. Cronbach's alpha is a general form of the Kuder-Richardson (K-R) 20 formulas used to access internal consistency of an instrument based on split-half reliabilities of data from all possible halves of the instrument. It reduces time required to compute a reliability coefficient in other methods (Mugenda&Mugenda, 2003).

The Kuder-Richardson (K-R) 20 is based on the following formula which will be used in order to make sure that questionnaire is valid and reliable. Content Validity Index (CVI) where the researcher computed the validity coefficient. The content validity index is equal to the total number of valid items divided by the total number of items. Thus, the content validity index (CVI) = $\frac{R}{R+IR}$ whereby R= relevant questions; IR= irrelevant questions. The instrument was certified the valid when its minimum content validity index is at least at 0.7 (Amin, 2005).

Reliability: In this research, Auditing committee is chosen before going at Nyamasheke District office where the distribution of 5 samples questionnaire was done for pre-testing the reliable result, thereafter, the result obtained is analyzed by using SPSS VERSION 20 for pre-testing of Cronbach's Alpha between the variables under study.

Table 1: Legend Cronbach's Test of Reliability

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.93$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable (Surveys)
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor

3.6.2 Validity of research instruments

An instrument is valid if it measures what it is intended to measure and accurately achieves the purpose for which it was designed (Patten, 2004; Wallen&Fraenkel, 2001). Validity is a matter of degree and no test instrument is perfectly valid, Patten, (2004). Validity involves the appropriateness, meaningfulness, and usefulness of inferences made by the researcher on the basis of the data collected (Wallen&Fraenkel, 2001). Content validity is determined by judgments on the appropriateness of the instrument's content, Patten (2004). There are three principles to improve content validity: Use of a broad sample of content rather than a narrow one, to emphasize on important material, and to write questions to measure the appropriate skill (Patten, 2004). The three Principles were considered in this study.

3.7. DATA ANALYSIS

Ms Word was used to report the whole work; SPSS software was used to analyze different data from interviews by making tables and graphs. Note that linear regression was used to show the correlation between two variables under the study.

Analysis was carried out using uni-variate and multi-variate statistical techniques as the multivariate decomposition techniques were used in the 1970s by many researchers for linear regression models and later extended to nonlinear models with an in-depth discussion on how to address the related weaknesses (Fairlie 2005; Powers and Pullum 2006), the analysis with descriptive results provided the frequencies of respondents for each independent variable and each survey, from which was shown, in percentage points.

While analyzing data, the researcher referred to rules and regulation of editing, coding and tabulation.

3.7.1. Editing

This involved the identification and corrections of errors found in questionnaires and attitude scale responses. It was done immediately after such responses are cross-checked to make sure that accuracy, completion and uniformity are purposefully reinforced.

3.7.2. Coding

Coding was applied for the transformation of gathered results from the field study into categories converted into codes for easy qualitative and quantitative analysis.

3.7.3. Tabulation

After carrying out editing and coding, frequency distribution tables were used. Tables were constructed according to the main themes in the questionnaires summarized all the findings of the study. Therefore, the results were presented in terms of frequencies and percentages.

Regression analysis included Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Regression of Coefficients.

ANOVA was used to test the significance level of the model using the 0.05 conventional level where a variable is said to be statistically significant if it falls within the conventional threshold of 0.05.

SUMMARY

This chapter presented the methodological perspectives of this study. The strategies adopted in the study to collect data are fully discussed in this chapter. The strategies included sample/sampling procedures and the questionnaire survey. Normally, research design and approaches, target population selection, sampling procedures, selecting sample size, data collection process, reliability and validity measurements and data analysis techniques were discussed in this chapter.

CHAPTER FOUR: ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0. Introduction

This chapter shows various methods which were used in data collection process and research design. Normally, it includes; description of used research approaches and the design of the study, the considered target population, procedures used in sampling, the considered sample size, the process of data collection, the reliability and validity of measurements of the study and the analysis method used for analyzing the collected data. This chapter shows also the analysis and below each table there is interpretation of findings.

4.1. Analysis and interpretation of findings

4.1.1. Identification of respondents

4.1.1.1. Analysis and interpretation of findings of pre-test for VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

To establish the reliability of the questionnaire, the researcher used pre-test method where the questionnaires were distributed to 5 employees of Auditing committee which is chosen purposively among Nyamasheke District committees working closely to PAC . The validity of instruments was measured by using the content validity Index (CVI) where the researcher computed the validity coefficient. The content validity index is equal to the total number of valid items divided by the total number of items. Thus, the content validity index (CVI) = $R/R+IR$ whereby R= relevant questions; IR= irrelevant questions. The instrument was certified the valid when its minimum content validity index is at least at 0.75

Total number of questionnaire = 5

Total number of valid questionnaire (R) = 5

Total number of Irrelevant questionnaire (IR) =0

Content validity index = $5 / (5+0) = 1$ The content validity index is 1 ; thus the instruments are certified valid because the content validity index is more than the required minimum which is 0.75

Reliability: Auditing committee was chosen before proceeding to other committees of Nyamasheke Distrcit working closely with PAC where the distribution of 5 sample questionnaires was distributed for pre-testing the reliable results. Therefore, the results obtained, they were

analyzed by using Statistical Packages for social sciences (SPSS) for pre-testing of Cronbach's Alpha between two variables.

Table 2: Legend Cronbach's Test of Reliability

Cronbach's alpha	Internal consistency
$\alpha \geq 0.9$	Excellent
$0.8 \leq \alpha < 0.93$	Good
$0.7 \leq \alpha < 0.8$	Acceptable (Surveys)
$0.6 \leq \alpha < 0.7$	Questionable
$0.5 \leq \alpha < 0.6$	Poor

Source: Legend Cronbach's Test of Reliability

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
1	5

Source: Pre-test of reliability 2019

The pre-test results from Auditing committee analyzed where by shown the reliability statistics of 1 (e.g.,100%) which categorized above $\alpha \geq 0.9$ and this is considered as Excellent according to legend Cronbach's Test of Reliability.

4.1.1.2. Distribution of respondents by gender

It was necessary to identify the gender of respondents while carrying out this research to know how much gender balance was considered.

Table 3: Distribution by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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	Male	16	69.6	69.6	69.6
Valid	Female	7	30.4	30.4	100.0
	Total	23	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 3 shows that along this study while selecting sample size, the respondents comprised male and female where the male represented 69.6% and female were 30.4% of the total considered respondents.

4.1.1.3. Distribution of respondents by Age

Age distribution was a key while carrying out this research to know the category which could provide with reliable ideas about the topic.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 19-35	2	8.7	8.7	8.7
36-45	10	43.5	43.5	52.2
45-65	11	47.8	47.8	100.0
Total	23	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 4 identifies the respondents considering their ages where 8.7% represented respondents between 19 and 35 years, 43.5% had between 36 and 45 and finally 47.8% had between 45 and 65 years

4.1.1.4. Distribution of respondents by marital status

The researcher endeavored in identifying respondents by their marital status.

Table 5: Distribution of respondents by marital status

Marital status	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid married	23	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 5 shows that all 23 respondents who represented 100 were married.

4.1.1.5. Distribution of respondents by level of education

Level of education was evaluated to know how much respondents could use their intellectual skills to respond to the questionnaire related to the topic.

Table 6: Distribution of respondents by level of education

Education level	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bachelors degree	5	21.7	21.7	21.7
Valid Masters degree and above	18	78.3	78.3	100.0
Total	23	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 6 demonstrates that among the respondents; 21.7% had bachelor's degree and 78.3% had master's degree.

4.1.2. Recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented

In this case the researcher evaluated the recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented.

Table 7: Recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Mean	Std deviation
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PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report	69.6%	30.4%	0%	0%	1.3043	0.47047
PAC provide with you recommendations to follow based on OAG observation	52.2%	47.8%	0%	0%	1.4783	0.51075
Recommendations raised and provided by PAC are implemented	65.2%	34.8%	0%	0%	1.3478	0.48698
PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly	47.8%	52.2%	0%	0%	1.5217	0.51075
PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly	60.9	39.1%	0%	0%	1.3913	0.49901
Average					1.40868	0.495592

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

In table 7 the researcher sought to know the recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented; in fact it was revealed that PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PAC provide with recommendations to follow based on OAG observation, it was revealed that recommendations raised and provided by PAC are implemented as 100% of respondents reported this situation, the respondents said again that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as 100% of respondents agreed to this statement and finally to this case it was shown that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed. The overall mean was 1.41 and overall standard deviation was 0.4496. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations are being implemented.

4.1.3. Time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed

It necessary to evaluate the time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed.

Table 8: Time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Mean	Std deviation
Regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned	69.6%	30.4%	0%	0%	1.3043	0.47047
PFM meeting help the execution of recommendation provided by PAC	56.5%	43.5%	0%	0%	1.4348	0.506887
Quarterly review of financial statement, Quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning are analyzed.	60.6%	39.1%	0%	0%	1.3913	0.49901
Recommendations raised by PAC are implemented	52.2%	47.8%	0%	0%	1.4783	0.51075
The implementation of PAC recommendation is satisfactory	26.1%	73.9%	0%	0%	1.7391	0.44898
Average					1.46956	0.487219

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 8 shows the time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed; actually it was revealed that regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PFM meeting help the execution of recommendation provided by PAC, the Quarterly review of financial statement, Quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning are analyzed as 100% of respondents reported this situation, it was reported that recommendations raised by PAC are implemented as it was pointed out by 100% Of respondents

and to this case again respondents said that the implementation of PAC recommendation is satisfactory as 100% of them agreed to this. The overall mean was 1.46956 and overall standard deviation was 0.487219. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that there is a regular time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and that they are executed.

4.1.4. Indicators of performance among local administrative entities

It necessary to evaluate indicators of performance among local administrative entities due to implementation of recommendations raised by PAC.

Table 9: Indicators of performance among local administrative entities

Statement	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Mean	Std deviation
The district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities.	65.2%	34.8%	0%	0%	1.3478	0.48698
Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations	78.3%	21.7%	0%	0%	1.2609	0.42174
Local entities performed efficiently due to PAC recommendations	73.9%	26.1%	0%	0%	1.2609	0.44898
Financial matters, Compliance matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations	73.9%	26.1%	0%	0%	1.2609	0.44898
Value for money matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations	65.2%	34.8%	0%	0%	1.3478	0.48698
Average					1.29566	0.458732

Source: Primary data, July, 2019

Table 9 shows the indicators of performance among local administrative entities due to implementation of recommendation raised by PAC; actually it was revealed that the district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents pointed out that Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations, actually Local entities performed efficiently due to PAC recommendations as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed to this situation, 100% of respondents agreed that Financial matters, Compliance matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations and Value for money matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations as 100% of respondents reported this situation. The overall mean was 1.29566 and overall standard deviation was 0.458732. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that the local entities in study area performed due to implementation of PAC recommendations.

4.1.5. Correlation between the performance and recommendations raised by PAC based OAG in study area

4.1.6. Regression analysis

The findings were analyzed using regression analysis ANOVA and regression of coefficient to evaluate whether PAC have impact on performance of local administration entities.

4.1.6.1. Fit analysis

Table 10: Fit analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.887 ^a	.787	.766	.21731

a. Predictors: (Constant), Follow_up_of_recommendation, Recommendation_raised_by_PAC

Table 10 shows the fitness of the regression model in explaining the variables under the study. The findings show that the predictor variables; Recommendation raised by PAC and Follow up of recommendations explained the performance of local entities in Nyamasheke district. R square of 0.787 (78.7%) supported the findings. This implies that the predictor variables (Recommendations raised by PAC and follow up of recommendations) can explain the performance of local administrative entities at 78.7% and the remaining 21.3% are explained by other variable which

were not studied in this research and the researcher recommend that that they could be put into consideration in future studies.

4.1.6.2. Analysis of variance

Table 11: Analysis of variance (ANOVA)

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.490	2	1.745	36.957	.000 ^b
	Residual	.944	20	.047		
	Total	4.435	22			

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Follow_up_of_recommendation, Recommendation_raised_by_PAC

Table 11 presented ANOVA statistics which indicates that the overall model was statistically significant. Probability (p) value of 0.000 supported this. The reported p was significant in this study because it was less than the conventional probability of 0.05 significance level. These results indicate that recommendations raised by PAC and Follow up of recommendations are good predictors of performance of local entities.

4.1.6.2. Regression of coefficients

Table 12: Regression of coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.111	.149		.744	.465
	Recommendation_raised_by_PAC	.472	.156	.408	3.031	.007
	Follow_up_of_recommendation	.472	.112	.569	4.230	.000
	n					

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

A linear regression line is used as an equation of the form $Y = a + bX$, where X is the explanatory variable and Y is the dependent variable. The slope of the line is b , and a is the intercept (the value of y when $x = 0$). The study uses linear regression by analyzing the performance in terms of recommendations raised by PAC and follow up of recommendations as independent variables, with

performance of local administrative entities in terms of “*performance*” as dependent variable. The study used the formula of $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \varepsilon$

Y is dependent variable indicator which is “performance of local administrative entities’ independent variable factors which are “recommendations raised by PAC and follow up of recommendations”.

The Linear Regression Test between implication of PAC and performance of local administrative entities show the result of;

$$y = 0.111 + 0.472X_1 + 0.472X_2 + \varepsilon$$

The X_1 represent recommendations raised by PAC and X_2 represent follow up of recommendations, and lastly ε represents standard errors. As explained by the linear regression equation, it is clear that one unit change of X_1 and X_2 , lead to change times 0.472 and 0.472 of dependent variable respectively. In the other case if all independent variable indicators are zero, the dependent variable equals to the constant (0.111).

Thus, according to the results indicated to the table 12, there is positive relationship between recommendations raised by PAC and follow up of recommendations to performance of local administrative entities.

- a) When Nyamasheke district adopts PAC recommendations only without other factors, result on the performance became

$$y = 0.111 + 0.472X_1 + .156$$

- b) Therefore, when Nyamasheke district used only follow up of recommendation , the performance was becoming

$$y = 0.111 + 0.472X_2 + .112$$

4.2. Discussion of findings

The findings of this study were discussed referring to the set objective and how they were attained while the investigation at the field.

4.2.1. Recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented

It was of great importance to know Recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented.

Results demonstrate that In table 6 the researcher sought to know the recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented; in fact it was revealed that PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PAC provide with recommendations to follow based on OAG observation, it was revealed that recommendations raised and provided by PAC are implemented as 100% of respondents reported this situation, the respondents said again that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as 100% of respondents agreed to this statement and finally to this case it was shown that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed. The overall mean was 1.41 and overall standard deviation was 0.4496. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations are being implemented.

4.2.2. Monitoring and evaluation of the progressive implementation of PAC and OAG recommendations

Table 7 shows the time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed; actually it was revealed that regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PFM meeting help the execution of recommendation provided by PAC, the Quarterly review of financial statement, Quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning are analyzed as 100% of respondents reported this situation, it was reported that recommendations raised by PAC are implemented as it was pointed out by 100% Of respondents and to this case again respondents said that the implementation of PAC recommendation is satisfactory as 100% of them agreed to this. The overall mean was 1.46956and overall standard deviation was 0.487219. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that there is a regular time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and that they are executed.

4.2.3. Indicators of performance in study area.

Table 8 shows the indicators of performance among local administrative entities due to implementation of recommendation raised by PAC; actually it was revealed that the district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities as reported

by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents pointed out that Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations, actually Local entities performed efficiently due to PAC recommendations as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed to this situation, 100% of respondents agreed that Financial matters, Compliance matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations and Value for money matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations as 100% of respondents reported this situation. The overall mean was 1.29566 and overall standard deviation was 0.458732. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that the local entities in study area performed due to implementation of PAC recommendations.

4.3. Summary of findings

The findings of this research were summarized following the set objective where it was found that; Referring to objective one it is obvious that; in table 6 the researcher sought to know the recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and how are being implemented; in fact it was revealed that PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PAC provide with recommendations to follow based on OAG observation, it was revealed that recommendations raised and provided by PAC are implemented as 100% of respondents reported this situation, the respondents said again that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as 100% of respondents agreed to this statement and finally to this case it was shown that PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed.

The second objective identified in table 7 the time of implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation and how they are executed; actually it was revealed that regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents said that PFM meeting help the execution of recommendation provided by PAC, the Quarterly review of financial statement, Quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning are analyzed as 100% of respondents reported this situation, it was reported that recommendations raised by PAC are implemented as it was pointed out by 100% Of respondents and to this case again respondents said that the implementation of

PAC recommendation is satisfactory as 100% of them agreed to this. The overall mean was 1.46956 and overall standard deviation was 0.487219. The findings imply that the respondents agreed in general that there is a regular time of implementation of PAC recommendations based on OAG observation and that they are executed.

The third objective revealed in table 8 the indicators of performance among local administrative entities due to implementation of recommendation raised by PAC; actually it was revealed that the district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities as reported by 100% of respondent who agreed to this statement; 100% of respondents pointed out that Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations, actually Local entities performed efficiently due to PAC recommendations as reported by 100% of respondents who agreed to this situation, 100% of respondents agreed that Financial matters, Compliance matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations and Value for money matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations as 100% of respondents reported this situation.

CHAPTER FIVE: CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.0. INTRODUCTION

This study was designed to assess the implication of PAC on performance of local administrative entities in study area. A sample of 23 respondents were selected using appropriate formula and they received questionnaires to give their views and opinion about what was been researched into. Afterward gathered ideas were analyzed, interpreted and finally discussed.

5.1. CONCLUSION

This study was interested on the implication of PAC on performance of local administrative entities in study area, actually the motivation for this research was that PAC contribute in giving and following up the recommendation about compliance matters, value for money matters and other related local administrative entities evaluation. The objectives of this study were; to assess the recommendations raised by PAC based OAG observations in study area, to monitor and evaluate the progressive implementation of PAC and OAG recommendation, to weigh the indicators of performance in study area and to find out the correlation between the performance and recommendations raised by PAC based OAG in study area.

By conclusion, it is clear from study area that PAC contribute in performance of local administrative entities found in study area. Normally, they have expanded and managed their daily operations and made effective decisions. Actually, they have moved from situations of multiple problems, particularly financial matters, Compliance matters and Value for money matters, to seeing themselves as viable in performance. They feel more secure because they can meet their effective daily operations and decision making. However, they are still facing some challenges in the integration of PAC recommendation in performance of their daily operations and once they are mitigated with proposed strategies the performance will be effectively increased.

5.2. RECOMMENDATION

The followings are proposed interventions that need to be implemented in order to ensure that the work of the PACs consistently improves:

1.Capacity building: Government should continuously capacitate PACs Members and support staff on effective oversight This can be done through training, professional skills development programs (recognized qualification), exchange programs, and study opportunities.

2. Building institutional memory: unless there is underperformance, Members and support staff of PACs must remain in the same Committee in order to build institutional memory and for easy tracking of resolutions.

3. Allocation of more resources: PACs need to be allocated with enough funds which can enable the Committee to effectively execute its functions.

4. Clearing work backlogs: workload can be cleared by holding two public hearings per annum. The acceptance of the proposed intervention also means that more funds must be allocated to perform that task.

5.3. Suggestion for further studies

For further studies the following studies could be looked into;

1. Effectiveness and Efficiency of Public Accounts Committees (PACs) in Enhancing Oversight and Accountability in the Public Sector.
2. The Role of Public Accounts Committees on public financial management
3. Accountability and the Public Accounts Committee

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1 : QUESTIONNAIRE AND INTERVIEW GUIDE

NDAYISENGA Innocent
Kibogora Polytechnic (K.P)
Faculty of Business and
Development Studies
Tel: +250789262062
Nyamasheke district
Western province of
Rwanda

Dear respondents,

I am a student at K.P in the Faculty of Business and Development Studies; I am conducting a research with title of implication of public accounts committee (PAC) on performance of local administrative entities in Rwanda

You were chosen to participate in answering the designed questions because you are one of the people who are concerned by this research. I wish you would kindly respond to the questions pointing on given objectives with honesty; the participation is voluntary and of high consideration.

I sincerely ensure you that, there will be no subsequent risks after having given your opinions and perceptions about what you will have responded. The information provided will be kept confidentially and will be used only for academic purposes.

If your answers focus on the questions that were asked.

Thank you very much for your kind and honest consideration to my request.

NDAYISENGA Innocent

PART I: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC OF RESPONDENTS

Please tick (V) in blanket concerning with your opinion

1. Gender

Female

Male

2. Age of respondent

19-35

36-45

45-65

66years and above

3. Marital status

Single

Married

Widow (er)

Divorced/separated

4. Level of education

Masters and above

Bachelors' degree

Secondary level

Other qualification specify.....

PART II: PUBLIC ACCOUNTS COMMITTEE (PAC) ON PERFORMANCE OF LOCAL ADMINISTRATIVE ENTITIES IN RWANDA

5. How recommendations raised by PAC basing on OAG observations and are being implemented?

		SA	A	D	SD
1	PAC involves in regular analysis of OAG report				
2	PAC provide with you recommendations to follow based on OAG observation				
3	Recommendations raised and provided by PAC are implemented				
4	PAC monitors the implementation of raised recommendations to local entities regularly				
5	PAC evaluates if recommendations were implemented and the outcome of implementation				

6. How and in which time implementation of PAC recommendations based OAG observation are executed?

		SA	A	D	SD
1	Regular time to carry out monthly PFM meeting is planned				
2	PFM meeting help the execution of recommendation provided by PAC				
3	Quarterly review of financial statement, Quarterly issue tracking of OAG recommendations and PFM Peer Learning are analyzed.				
4	Recommendations raised by PAC are implemented				
5	The implementation of PAC recommendation is satisfactory				

7. What are indicators of performance among local administrative entities?

		SA	A	D	S D
1	The district performed in, Social, health, agriculture, education, infrastructures and other entities.				
2	Local administrative entities executed PAC recommendations				

3	Local entities performed efficiently due to PAC recommendations				
4	Financial matters, Compliance matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations				
5	Value for money matters are encountered and resolved due to PAC recommendations				

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATION